

Supplementary Material of “Towards Feature Selection in High-dimensional Data: A Multi-task Evolution Strategy Aided with Symmetrical Uncertainty and Attention”

Xinkai Liao¹, Yanghui Mao¹, Yuren Zhou²(✉), and Zefeng Chen¹(✉)

¹ School of Artificial Intelligence, Sun Yat-sen University, Zhuhai 519082, China

² School of Software Engineering, Sun Yat-sen University, Zhuhai 519082, China

1 Preliminaries

1.1 Feature Selection

Feature selection (FS) is a fundamental data-driven optimization problem aimed at identifying an optimal subset of features from a high-dimensional dataset. Given a dataset \mathcal{D} with D features, the FS problem can be mathematically formulated as a combinatorial optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{X}} \quad & F(\mathbf{X}) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \mathbf{X} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_D), \\ & x_d \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall d \in \{1, 2, \dots, D\} \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where the objective function F represents an evaluation metric of a downstream machine learning model, such as the classification error rate of a classifier. Here, $x_d = 1$ means that the d -th feature is included in the subset, while $x_d = 0$ indicates its exclusion.

1.2 Multi-task Optimization

Multi-task optimization (MTO) aims to simultaneously solve multiple tasks (each being an optimization problem), thereby exploiting shared knowledge among them to enhance the optimization of each individual task. Without loss of generality, an MTO problem involving K tasks (each task \mathcal{T}_k is a minimization problem and its objective function is denoted as F_k) can be formulated as follows: $(\mathbf{x}_1^*, \dots, \mathbf{x}_K^*) = \operatorname{argmin}\{F_1, \dots, F_K\}$, where \mathbf{x}_k^* represents the optimal solution of \mathcal{T}_k .

In the realm of EC, this paradigm is referred to as Evolutionary Multitasking (EMT) [5, 6]. Since its inception, EMT has garnered widespread attention for its potential to improve search efficiency through implicit or explicit knowledge transfer [1, 4, 8].

1.3 Symmetrical Uncertainty

Symmetrical uncertainty (SU) is an information-theoretic measure of feature relevance derived from entropy. It can effectively capture the numerous non-linear feature interactions present in a high-dimensional dataset by measuring the shared information between features and class label. The mathematical formulation of SU is: $SU(f_i, C) = \frac{2 \cdot I(f_i; C)}{H(f_i) + H(C)}$, where $H(f_i)$ and $H(C)$ respectively denote the entropy of feature f_i and class label C , while $I(f_i; C)$ represents their information gain. Note that continuous features must be discretized prior to computing SU [16].

In essence, SU normalizes the information value to the range $[0, 1]$, with 0 indicating no relationship and 1 representing complete dependency [14]. This metric offers two key advantages: first, the SU can compensate for the inherent bias of mutual information toward features with high cardinality; second, the symmetry property of SU is especially advantageous for the high-dimensional problems under investigation, providing an unbiased metric for feature selection in high-dimensional spaces.

1.4 OpenAI-ES

The OpenAI-ES algorithm [12] was originally designed to demonstrate the effectiveness of ES-like methods on reinforcement learning tasks. Due to its simplicity and efficiency, it has been widely used as the underlying optimizer in various subsequent ES variants of the algorithm, such as the multi-task optimization algorithm MTES [1]. The algorithm process of OpenAI-ES is concise: N individuals are sampled from a Gaussian distribution $(\theta, \sigma^2 I)$, their fitness values are then computed using an objective function, and parameters are updated based on fitness scores and genotypes. The algorithmic steps of OpenAI-ES are outlined in **Algorithm 1**.

Algorithm 1 Pseudocode of OpenAI-ES

Input: Dataset

Parameter: Population size N , Standard deviation σ , Learning rate α , Initial distribution parameters θ^0

Output: Best solution

- 1: Set $t = 0$
 - 2: **while** stopping criterion is not met **do**
 - 3: **for** $i = 1$ to N **do**
 - 4: Draw sample $\epsilon_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$
 - 5: Compute fitness $F_i = F(\theta^t + \sigma \epsilon_i)$
 - 6: **end for**
 - 7: $\theta^{t+1} = \theta^t - \alpha \frac{1}{N\sigma} \sum_{i=1}^N F_i \epsilon_i$
 - 8: $t = t + 1$
 - 9: **end while**
 - 10: **return** Best solution derived from θ^t
-

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of constructing three low-dimensional FS tasks ($D_s = 5$).

2 More Details about Our Proposed SAMTES

2.1 Pseudocode for SAMTES

The pseudocode of the proposed SAMTES is presented in **Algorithm 2**.

2.2 Three Heterogeneous Tasks

The diagrams for constructing three heterogeneous tasks are shown in Figure 1.

3 Reproducibility

3.1 Empirical Studies

All experiments were implemented in Python and executed on a workstation equipped with a 12th Gen Intel Core i7-12700KF CPU and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 GPU.

Detailed Information of Datasets The details of the datasets used in this paper are summarized in Table 1. These datasets are publicly accessible at <https://jundong1.github.io/scikit-feature/datasets.html> and the UCI Machine Learning Repository³.

Since the computation of SU requires the features to be of a discrete type, the quantile discretization (with $n_bin = 5$) is conducted on the features of continuous type.

Encoding Scheme EC algorithms were initially developed for continuous optimization problems; therefore, we cannot directly apply them to discrete FS classification problems. To address this limitation, we introduce an encoding function. To maintain consistency in the encoding approach, we employ a straightforward binarization method after initializing the population by sampling the initial distribution values for each individual's features in the EC algorithms

³ <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/169/dorothea>

Algorithm 2 Pseudocode of Proposed SAMTES

Input: Dataset**Parameter:** Population size for all tasks N , Objective function F , Dimension of dataset D , Standard deviation σ , Learning rate α , Weight coefficient w_{aux} **Output:** Best solution

- 1: Construct 3 low-dimensional tasks based on SU, and use **Resource Allocation** to get $N_k (\forall k \in \{1, \dots, 3\})$
 - 2: Initialize parameters $\theta_k^0, \forall k$; Set $t = 0$
 - 3: **while** stopping criterion is not met **do**
 - 4: **for** $k = 1$ to 3 **do**
 - 5: **for** $n = 1$ to N_k **do**
 - 6: Draw sample $\epsilon_k^n \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I), \quad \epsilon_k^n \in \mathbb{R}^D$
 - 7: Construct candidate solution $x_k^n = \theta_k^t + \sigma \epsilon_k^n$
 - 8: Compute fitness $F_k^n = F(\theta_k^t + \sigma \epsilon_k^n)$
 - 9: Normalize fitness $NF_k^n = \frac{F_k^n - \text{mean}(F_k)}{\text{std}(F_k)}$
 - 10: **end for**
 - 11: **end for**
 - 12: **if** $t = 0$ **then**
 - 13: **for** $k = 1$ to 3 **do**
 - 14: Update \mathcal{T}_k 's distribution: $\theta_k^{t+1} = \theta_k^t - \alpha \frac{1}{N_k \sigma} \sum_{n=1}^{N_k} NF_k^n \epsilon_k^n$
 - 15: **end for**
 - 16: **else**
 - 17: **for** $k = 1$ to 3 **do**
 - 18: **for** $i = 1$ to 3 **do**
 - 19: Set $N_{elite} = \lfloor N_i/2 \rfloor$
 - 20: Set $F_i = \sum_{n=1}^{N_{elite}} F_i^n$
 - 21: $C_i = \sum_{n=1}^{N_{elite}} (F_i^n / F_i) x_i^n$
 - 22: **end for**
 - 23: Set $\mathbf{Q}_k = C_k, \mathbf{K}_k = \mathbf{V}_k = [C_1; \dots; C_{k-1}; C_{k+1}; \dots; C_3]$
 - 24: Compute the knowledge vector $\kappa_k = \text{Softmax}(\mathbf{Q}_k \mathbf{K}_k^T) \mathbf{V}_k$
 - 25: Set $w_k = 1 - w_{aux}$
 - 26: Update \mathcal{T}_k 's distribution: $\theta_k^{t+1} = w_{aux} \kappa_k + w_k \theta_k^t - \alpha \frac{1}{N_k \sigma} \sum_{n=1}^{N_k} NF_k^n \epsilon_k^n$
 - 27: **end for**
 - 28: **end if**
 - 29: Determine the best solution (denoted as x_{best}^t) from all candidate solutions of all tasks in t -th iteration
 - 30: $t = t + 1$
 - 31: **end while**
 - 32: **return** Best solution found so far
-

Table 1: Specification of all datasets used in our experiments

Dataset	#Instances	#Features (D)	#Classes	Type
colon	62	2000	2	discrete
PCMAC	1943	3289	2	discrete
lymphoma	96	4026	9	discrete
RELATHE	1427	4322	2	discrete
BASEHOCK	1993	4862	2	discrete
Leukemia	72	7070	2	discrete
nci9	60	9712	9	discrete
arcene	200	10000	2	continuous
CLL_SUB_111	111	11340	3	continuous
SMK_CAN_187	187	19993	2	continuous
GLI_85	85	22283	2	continuous
Dorothea	800	100000	2	discrete

under consideration. Assuming a distribution range of $[0, 1]$, a simple example is as follows:

$$x_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y_i > 0.5 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where 0.5 represents the midpoint of the value range, with 0 indicating feature non-selection and 1 indicating feature selection. The variable y_i represents the real-valued number of a population individual, corresponding to the genotype, and the variable x_i represents the mapping result for the i -th feature of the individual, corresponding to the phenotype.

However, the MCC-NES algorithm introduces a specialized discretization method, referencing the structure and characteristics of the Sigmoid function to design a novel encoding function. This maps the numerical result for a given feature to a Boolean type (i.e., 0 or 1), where 1 represents the selection of that feature and 0 indicates it is not selected. The specific feature encoding function is given by Equation 3.

$$x_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \frac{1}{1+e^{-y_i}} > 0.5 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

To ensure a consistent comparison, almost every method implements explicit binary selection with Equation 2. The only exception to this is the MCC-NES algorithm, which employs its specified encoding method (Equation 3).

Objective Function In our experiments, the objective function is defined as a weighted sum of the classification error rate and the feature subset ratio. The fitness value is formulated as follows:

$$Fitness = \omega \cdot ER + (1 - \omega) \cdot \frac{|S|}{D} \quad (4)$$

where ER denotes the classification error rate, $|S|$ represents the number of selected features. To ensure a fair comparison, the weight parameter ω is set to 0.999999 for most algorithms. Exceptions are made for MEL and MTPSO, where ω is set to 0.9 to align with their original implementations and source code settings.

Parameter Settings for All Algorithms For all algorithms, we set the maximum number of fitness evaluations to 2000, the number of independent runs to 21, and the number of candidate solutions in each iteration to $N = 200$.

The parameter settings used for all algorithms are detailed in Table 2.

Table 2: Parameter settings for all algorithms

Algorithms	Parameter values
SAMTES	The learning rate $\alpha = 0.1$, the noise standard deviation $\sigma = 0.1$, the size of each task’s feature subspace: $D_s = D/20$, the weight coefficients: $w_{aux} = 0.10$, the transfer interval $G=1$
AMFEA	$g_1 = 0.1$, $g_2 = g_3 = g_4 = 0.45$, the threshold value of Spearman’s method $\mu_S = 0.5$, the threshold value of the TV method $\mu_T = 0.05$, the percentage of selected features in the total set sorted by importance using Relief-F $\mu_R = 0.2$, RMP = $\begin{bmatrix} 0.5 & \cdots & 0.5 \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ 0.5 & \cdots & 0.5 \end{bmatrix}$, the weight parameter used in the fitness function is set to 0.999999 [9]
MEL	With the exception of the weighting parameter for error rate and compression ratio, set to $w = [1, 0]$, all other parameters were kept consistent with the open-source code https://github.com/wangxb96/MEL [15].
MTPSO	$c_1 = c_2 = 1.49445$, $w = 0.9 - 0.5 * (iter/max_iter)$, random mating probability $rmf = 0.6$, the max iterations for updating velocity using the united information $G = 6$ [3].
CMAwM	Coordinate-wise standard deviation $\sigma = 0.5$, $\alpha = (N\lambda)^{-1}$, which determines the margin in the CMAwM, and default CMA-ES settings were used for all remaining parameters [7].
MCC-NES	The learning rate $\alpha = 0.02$, the number of populations $O = 3$, the number of subpopulations $S = 3$, the restart threshold $W = 9$, and historical utilization rate $\beta = 0.6$ [10].
OpenAI-ES	The learning rate $\alpha = 0.1$, the noise standard deviation $\sigma = 0.1$ [12].
FCBF	The predefined threshold $\delta = 0.01$, other parameters were kept consistent with the open-source code in this link: https://github.com/SantiagoEG/FCBF_module [13]
Other Algorithms	Other non-EC algorithms are parameterized with reference to default settings in sklearn library (see https://scikit-learn.org/stable/api/sklearn.feature_selection.html for details [2, 11]).

Table 3: Comparisons of average number of selected features obtained by different algorithms with 1-NN classifier across medium-to-high dimensional datasets. (SAM: SAMTES, AMF: AMFEA, MTP: MTPSO, CMA: CMAwM, MCC: MCC-NES, OES: OpenAI-ES)

Dataset	D	SAM	AMF	MEL	MTP	CMA	MCC	OES
colon	2000	21.0±3.5	96.3±54.4	466.4±345.7	386.1±83.3	990.2±32.1	442.8±109.3	985.6±14.3
PCMAC	3289	40.4±4.4	153.3±139.1	1251.6±164.9	454.0±157.7	1662.5±21.1	1194.0±154.2	1636.8±32.4
lymphoma	4026	34.5±3.1	121.6±100.2	1439.4±88.5	1021.7±169.7	1990.3±39.0	652.7±144.0	1994.7±28.6
RELATHE	4322	57.6±6.2	1773.6±188.0	1634.6±394.0	221.0±47.2	2143.5±33.5	1570.3±202.6	2147.1±32.7
BASEHOCK	4862	58.7±4.6	466.8±86.0	1873.8±125.0	861.1±133.7	2423.5±35.4	1881.2±422.5	2433.3±30.5
Leukemia	7070	41.1±4.7	10.0±4.4	2257.7±904.4	1964.3±356.1	3523.1±29.1	1702.8±366.4	3528.4±45.7
nci9	7070	71.8±4.2	63.2±78.4	2678.6±1285.5	2441.7±352.1	4762.4±44.5	1378.4±352.9	4792.6±46.9

Table 4: Comparisons of average number of selected features obtained by different algorithms with 1-NN classifier across ultra-high dimensional datasets.

Dataset	D	SAMTES	AMFEA	MEL	MTPSO
arcene	10000	107.7±5.7	4960.1±58.5	3650.9±399.2	1655.7±277.2
CLL SUB 111	11340	99.2±10.7	8.9±3.4	1572.0±157.8	4075.9±470.5
SMK CAN 187	19993	168.8±14.7	69.9±198.8	2771.5±278.2	4247.8±824.8
GLI 85	22283	187.5±20.4	78.9±78.2	6490.4±3435.8	4784.3±840.6
Dorothea	100000	778.7±22.6	3.3±1.3	456.7±556.7	20277.3±3787.7

Regarding non-evolutionary baselines, we utilize several representative statistical filters. Specifically, ReliefF selects features with weights exceeding 0.01. FCBF enhances SU-based selection by identifying predominant correlations to remove redundancies. Additionally, three univariate techniques from Scikit-learn [2]—SelectFdr, SelectFwe, and SelectKBest—are employed using the chi-squared test. For these, we set the significance threshold $\alpha = 0.01$ for SelectFdr/SelectFwe and $K=20$ for SelectKBest.

3.2 The Detailed Information of Comparison with Non-EC Algorithms

The detailed performance comparison between SAMTES and traditional non-EC feature selection algorithms is summarized in Table 5.

As shown in Table 5, SAMTES achieves superior classification performance in most cases. Specifically, its accuracy significantly surpasses those of the five baseline FS algorithms across nearly all datasets.

3.3 Feature Subset Size Analysis and Generalization Verification for SAMTES

This section demonstrates the superiority of SAMTES in high-dimensional scenarios. Compared to existing multi-task EC-based methods, SAMTES exhibits

Table 5: Classification accuracies of SAMTES and classical non-EC FS methods. Results in black backgrounds indicate the best.

Dataset	D	SAMTES	RF	FCBF	Fdr	Fwe	KBest
colon	2000	0.975±0.012	0.745	0.776	0.000	0.000	0.776
PCMAC	3289	0.878±0.007	0.645	0.710	0.642	0.620	0.635
lymphoma	4026	0.633±0.000	0.917	0.938	0.000	0.000	0.667
RELATHE	4322	0.806±0.009	0.602	0.685	0.631	0.611	0.611
BASEHOCK	4862	0.941±0.006	0.735	0.887	0.860	0.746	0.707
Leukemia	7070	1.000±0.000	0.931	0.972	0.593	0.593	0.946
nci9	9712	0.427±0.010	0.467	0.617	0.150	0.150	0.283

not only higher classification performance but also yields small feature subset sizes

Feature Subset Size Analysis From Table 3 and Table 4, SAMTES maintains a comparable average subset size, highlighting an effective balance between model complexity and classification performance. In terms of classification performance, SAMTES significantly outperforms all competing multi-task frameworks across all datasets. Regarding the dimension reduction rate, SAMTES achieves the second-best results with only a marginal gap compared to the top performer, thereby striking an ideal balance between accuracy and feature sparsity.

Generalization Verification Furthermore, to evaluate the generalization capability of SAMTES, we employ an MLP as the underlying classifier, benchmarking SAMTES against competing algorithms on one representative dataset. As illustrated in Figure 2, both the performance and convergence rate of SAMTES remain highly competitive when the MLP architecture is adopted. Specifically, SAMTES achieves an accuracy improvement of approximately 5% over the runner-up, AMFEA. These results further demonstrate the robustness and broad applicability of the proposed SAMTES algorithm across different classifiers.

3.4 Parameter Sensitivity Experiments

Performance of SAMTES under Different Settings of Weight Coefficient w_{aux} First, in contrast to the traditional OpenAI-ES, SAMTES incorporates the external knowledge κ_k to assist in updating the θ_k of task \mathcal{T}_k . Therefore, the proportion of κ_k (that is, w_{aux}) in the updating formula significantly impacts the final performance of the algorithm. A smaller weight fails to convey sufficient information, while an excessively large weight can easily introduce redundant information. The related results are shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 2: Convergence curves of compared algorithms using MLP classifier

Fig. 3: Performance comparison of SAMTES with different values of w_{aux} on various datasets

Fig. 4: Performance comparison of SAMTES with different settings of interval on various datasets

Performance of SAMTES under Different Settings of Transfer Interval The transfer interval G modulates the frequency of inter-task knowledge exchange. We evaluated SAMTES with $G \in \{1, 3, 5\}$, and the results are illustrated in Figure 4.

References

1. Bai, L., Lin, W., Gupta, A., Ong, Y.S.: From multitask gradient descent to gradient-free evolutionary multitasking: A proof of faster convergence. *IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics* **52**(8), 8561–8573 (2021)
2. Buitinck, L., Louppe, G., Blondel, M., Pedregosa, F., Mueller, A., Grisel, O., Niculae, V., Prettenhofer, P., Gramfort, A., Grobler, J., Layton, R., VanderPlas, J., Joly, A., Holt, B., Varoquaux, G.: API design for machine learning software: experiences from the scikit-learn project. In: *ECML PKDD Workshop: Languages for Data Mining and Machine Learning*. pp. 108–122 (2013)
3. Chen, K., Xue, B., Zhang, M., Zhou, F.: Evolutionary multitasking for feature selection in high-dimensional classification via particle swarm optimization. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* **26**(3), 446–460 (2022)
4. Ding, J., Yang, C., Jin, Y., Chai, T.: Generalized multitasking for evolutionary optimization of expensive problems. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* **23**(1), 44–58 (2017)
5. Gupta, A., Ong, Y.S., Feng, L.: Multifactorial evolution: Toward evolutionary multitasking. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* **20**(3), 343–357 (2015)
6. Gupta, A., Ong, Y.S., Feng, L., Tan, K.C.: Multiobjective multifactorial optimization in evolutionary multitasking. *IEEE transactions on cybernetics* **47**(7), 1652–1665 (2016)
7. Hansen, N.: The cma evolution strategy: A tutorial. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1604.00772* (2016)
8. Li, Y., Gong, W., Li, S.: Multitask evolution strategy with knowledge-guided external sampling. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation* **28**(6), 1733–1745 (2023)
9. Li, Z., Li, H., Gao, W., Xie, J., Slowik, A.: Feature selection in high-dimensional classification via an adaptive multifactor evolutionary algorithm with local search. *Applied Soft Computing* **169**, 112574 (2025)
10. Li Zhanshan, Z.X.: Research on feature selection algorithm based on natural evolution strategy. *Journal of Software* **31**(12), 3733–3757 (2020)
11. Pedregosa, F., Varoquaux, G., Gramfort, A., Michel, V., Thirion, B., Grisel, O., Blondel, M., Prettenhofer, P., Weiss, R., Dubourg, V., Vanderplas, J., Passos, A., Cournapeau, D., Brucher, M., Perrot, M., Duchesnay, E.: Scikit-learn: Machine learning in Python. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* **12**, 2825–2830 (2011)
12. Salimans, T., Ho, J., Chen, X., Sidor, S., Sutskever, I.: Evolution strategies as a scalable alternative to reinforcement learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1703.03864* (2017)
13. Senliol, B., Gulgezen, G., Yu, L., Cataltepe, Z.: Fast correlation based filter (fcbf) with a different search strategy. In: *2008 23rd international symposium on computer and information sciences*. pp. 1–4. IEEE (2008)
14. Teukolsky, S.A., Flannery, B.P., Press, W., Vetterling, W.: Numerical recipes in c. *SMR* **693**(1), 59–70 (1992)
15. Wang, X., Shangguan, H., Huang, F., Wu, S., Jia, W.: Mel: efficient multi-task evolutionary learning for high-dimensional feature selection. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* **36**(8), 4020–4033 (2024)
16. Yu, L., Liu, H.: Feature selection for high-dimensional data: A fast correlation-based filter solution. In: *Proceedings of the 20th international conference on machine learning (ICML-03)*. pp. 856–863 (2003)